

**11th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
“FUNDAMENTAL AND APPLIED PROBLEMS OF MODERN PHYSICS”
Dedicated to 110th Anniversary of Academician S.A. Azimov**

**11-я МЕЖДУНАРОДНАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ
«ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ И ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ФИЗИКИ»
Посвящённая 110-летию академика С.А. Азимова**

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

ТРУДЫ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОЙ КОНФЕРЕНЦИИ

110

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UZBEKISTAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES
S.A. AZIMOV PHYSICAL-TECHNICAL INSTITUTE
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**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ
И ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ
СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ФИЗИКИ**

**FUNDAMENTAL AND APPLIED
PROBLEMS OF MODERN PHYSICS**

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OF INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE**

16 - 18 октября

Ташкент 2025 г.

**АКАДЕМИЯ НАУК РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН
ФИЗИКО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКИЙ ИНСТИТУТ ИМЕНИ С.А. АЗИМОВА
СОВЕТ ФИЗИКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА
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ВВЕДЕНИЕ

Физико-технический институт (ФТИ), основанный в 1943 году, является одним из старейших научных учреждений Академии наук Узбекистана. За годы своей деятельности институт сыграл важную роль в формировании многих научных направлений, которые впоследствии стали основными областями исследований в Академии наук Узбекистана. Среди них физическая электроника, физика твёрдого тела, физика полупроводников, ядерная физика, физика высоких энергий и космических лучей, технологии солнечной энергетики и материаловедение высоких температур. На базе научных направлений и подразделений ФТИ были созданы Институт ядерной физики (1956 г.), Институт электроники (1967 г.), и в 1987 г. - НПО "Физика-Солнце" АН РУз. Институт материаловедения организован в 1993 г. на базе ряда лабораторий ФТИ и его Опытного производства с Большой Солнечной Печью (БСП).

Признанием заслуг ученых НПО "Физика-Солнце" АН РУз явилось издание Указа Президента РУз №УП-4512 от 01.03.2013 г. «О мерах по дальнейшему развитию альтернативных источников энергии» и Постановления Президента РУз №ПП-1929 от 01.03.2013г. «О создании Международного института солнечной энергии». За крупный вклад в науку в области физики полупроводников в 2007 г. сотрудники Института академик М.С.Саидов, доктора ф.-м.н. И.Г. Атабаев и А.С. Саидов удостоены Государственной премии Республики Узбекистан в области науки и техники. За разработку и создание современных систем прямого преобразования солнечного излучения в электрическую энергию на основе кремниевых фотопреобразователей, коллектив ученых Института - С. Дадамухамедов, Х. Сабилов, М.Н. Турсунов, И.А. Юлдашев во главе с академиком Р.А. Муминовым удостоен в 2013 г. Государственной премии Республики Узбекистан в области науки и техники.

В Институте длительное время работали и работают в настоящее время видные ученые-физики: академик С.А. Азимов - основатель научной школы физики высоких и сверхвысоких энергий, высокотемпературного гелиоматериаловедения в нашей стране; академик У.А. Арифов – создатель школы физической электроники в Узбекистане; академики С.У. Умаров, Э.И. Адирович, М.С. Саидов и Р.А. Муминов – основатели различных направлений физики полупроводников, академик С.В. Стародубцев – создатель научной школы физики твёрдого тела и один из организаторов Института ядерной физики, член – корр. АН РУз Г.Я. Умаров – основатель научной школы гелиотехнических исследований в нашей Республике, академик Т.Т. Рискиев, создавший совместно с академиком С.А. Азимовым школу высокотемпературного материаловедения, академики К.Г. Гуламов, Б.С. Юлдашев и Т.С. Юлдашбаев, которые развили научную школу физики высоких энергий и космических лучей, основанную академиком С.А. Азимовым.

С 1965 г. ФТИ АН РУз издаёт Международный журнал «Гелиотехника». Журнал переводится на английский язык американской компанией «Аллертон Пресс», издаётся в США под названием «Applied Solar Energy» и распространяется по подписке. Журнал «Applied Solar Energy» индексируется в научной базе «SCOPUS» престижных международных журналов.

В этом 2025 году в Физико-техническом институте имени С.А.Азимова Академии наук Республики Узбекистан уже в одиннадцатый раз проводится ставшая традиционной Международная конференция «Фундаментальные и прикладные проблемы современной физики». В этот раз мероприятие посвящено 110-летию со дня рождения выдающегося учёного, академика Садыка Азимова.

Для участия в конференции принимались научные работы, выполненные в последние годы по следующим направлениям:

1. физика ядра и элементарных частиц (включая прикладные аспекты, физику высоких энергий и космических лучей); 2. физика полупроводников и твёрдого тела (в том числе физика плазмы и её приложения); 3. возобновляемые источники энергии и их использование (включая гелиоматериаловедение).

Приятно отметить, что по тематике конференции было подано 185 научных работ, среди которых 74 от зарубежных учёных из США, Японии, России, Пакистана, Казахстана, Азербайджана, Турции, Беларуси, Таджикистана и других стран.

Мы убеждены, что данная конференция станет эффективной площадкой для обмена новейшими научными достижениями между исследователями из разных стран, а также будет способствовать развитию новых научных связей и формированию перспективных международных коллабораций.

Председатель оргкомитета – проф., д.ф.-м.н. Хусниддин Олимов

INTRODUCTION

Founded in 1943, the Physical-Technical Institute (PhTI) is one of the oldest research institutions of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences. Over the years, it has played a key role in shaping many scientific disciplines that later became the core research areas of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences (UZAS). These include physical electronics, solid-state physics, semiconductor physics, nuclear physics, high-energy and cosmic ray physics, solar energy technologies, and high-temperature materials science.

On the basis of scientific areas and divisions of PhTI, several institutions were created, such as the Institute of Nuclear Physics (1956), Institute of Electronics (1967) and SPA “Physics-Sun” of the UzAS (1987). The Institute of Materials Science, based on a number of laboratories of PhTI and its pilot production facility with a Big Solar Furnace (BSF), was established in 1993.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures for further development of alternative energy sources” №UP-4512 on 01.03.2013 and the corresponding Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the establishment of the International Institute of solar energy” №PP-1929 on 01.03.2013 are recognition of achievements of scientists from PhTI of SPA “Physics-Sun” of the UzAS. For important contribution to science in the field of semiconductor physics, the Institute scientists - Academician M.S. Saidov, Dr. Sci. A.S. Saidov and Dr. Sci. I.G. Atabaev, were awarded the State Prize of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of science and technology in 2007. The team of scientists of the Institute - S. Dadamuhamedov, H. Sabirov, M.N. Tursunov, and I.A. Yuldashev, headed by Academician R.A. Muminov, was awarded in 2013 the State Prize of Uzbekistan in the field of science and technology for the development and creation of modern systems of direct conversion of solar radiation into electrical energy, based on silicon solar cells.

Many prominent physicists have worked in the past and are presently working at the institute. They founded the different well-known scientific schools and research directions in Uzbekistan: academician S.A. Azimov - founder of the scientific school of high-energy and ultra-high-energy physics and high-temperature materials science; academician U.A. Arifov - creator of the School of Physical Electronics; academicians S.U. Umarov, E.I. Adirovich, M.S. Saidov and R.A. Muminov - founders of various research areas in Semiconductor Physics; academician S.V. Starodubtsev – founder of scientific school of solid state physics and one of the founders of the Institute of Nuclear Physics; correspondent-member of UzAS G.Ya.Umarov – founder of the scientific school in applied solar energy research; academician T.T. Riskiev, who created, together with academician S.A. Azimov, the school of high temperature materials science; academicians K.G. Gulamov, B.S. Yuldashev, and T.S. Yuldashbaev, who developed further the scientific school of high energy and cosmic ray physics, founded by academician S.A. Azimov.

Since 1965, PhTI publishes the international journal “Applied Solar Energy”. The journal is translated into English by the American company “Allerton Press” and is published in the United States and distributed by subscription. The journal “Applied Solar Energy” is indexed in the “SCOPUS” scientific database of the prestigious international journals.

In 2025, the Physical-Technical Institute named after S.A. Azimov of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan is hosting, for the eleventh time, the traditional International Conference on “Fundamental and Applied Problems of Modern Physics.” This year, the event is dedicated to the 110th anniversary of the birth of the outstanding scientist, Academician Sadyk Azimov.

Scientific papers completed in recent years were accepted for participation in the following fields:

1. Nuclear and elementary particle physics (including applied aspects, high-energy physics, and cosmic rays);
2. Semiconductor and solid-state physics (including plasma physics and its applications);
3. Renewable energy sources and their applications (including heliomaterials science).

It is gratifying to note that 185 scientific papers were submitted to the conference, including 74 from foreign researchers representing the USA, Japan, Russia, Pakistan, Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan, Turkey, Belarus, Tajikistan, and other countries.

We are confident that this conference will serve as an effective platform for the exchange of the latest scientific achievements among researchers from different countries and will contribute to the development of new scientific collaborations and the establishment of promising international partnerships.

Chair of the organizing committee – Prof. Dr. Khusniddin Olimov

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AGE DETERMINATION OF THE SAMPLE TAKEN FROM GOBUSTAN IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

The presented work was the first attempt to increase the accuracy of dating natural archeological monuments, namely, the Boyukdash in Gobustan of Azerbaijan Republic, by employing the Thermoluminescent (TL) dating method. This method is based on the effect of the accumulation of nonequilibrium charge carriers on defects in dielectrics, which is generated by ionizing radiation from natural radionuclides contained in dating objects or their environment. The thermoluminescent method is a well-established method for determining the age of archaeological ceramics. Quartz inclusion method is employed for the Thermoluminescent dating. The technique to prepare the sample is described below. To eliminate the impact of β -emission on the dose absorbed in the past, 2mm thick outer layer of the sample is extracted with special tools. Acquired fragments are first crumbled, and then gently crushed in an agate mortar. Non-magnetic part of fragments was separated through magnets. Too large crystal grains ($> 200 \mu\text{m}$) are separated using laboratory sieves¹. Crystals with diameters 90-150 μm are used for thermoluminescent dating. To purify crystals from other minerals, first, they are soaked in 10 % Hydrochloric Acid solution for a day and then kept in 30 % Hydrogen Peroxide for 2 hours. To separate quartz grains from other crystals heavy liquids²³, like sodium polytungstate (2,5 - 3 g/sm³) are used. To eliminate the effect of alpha particles radiated by Uranium and Thorium on dose absorbed by crystal grains, they are soaked in (1N Hydrofluoric Acid) for 100 minutes. At this stage minerals such as Calcite and Feldspar are discarded. Quartz grains were divided into six equal parts and each aliquot was placed inside glass tubes (Suprasil) for laboratory irradiation⁴⁵. The samples were irradiated using a ⁶⁰Co source. A dose rate of the ⁶⁰Co source has been determined by Magnostech MiniscopeMS400 EPR Spectrometer using individually wrapped, barcode-labeled BioMax Alanine Dosimeter Films (developed by Eastman Kodak Company). In nature, the objects were irradiated at a very low dose rate conditions to compare with the laboratory irradiation. Dose mapping exercise has been conducted at three fixed locations around ⁶⁰Co source and dose rates were 0.194Gy/s, 0.0194Gy/s and 0.0098Gy/s consequently.

Harshaw TLD 3500 Manual Reader is used for the measuring TL characteristics of samples. In order to determine the natural dose rate soil samples were collected in close proximity to the pottery sample. Uranium, Thorium and Potassium concentrations in soil were measured by gamma spectrometry Canberra GR4520 which has a low-level gamma spectrometry system with 15 cm lead shielding and high-resolution GeHP hyper-pure germanium detector, having 43.5% resolution efficiency for 661.6 keV. Samples were irradiated with ⁶⁰Co gamma source then TL glow-curves measured after two days⁶.

Soil sample collected from the proximity of the pottery sample was air-dried and kept in a closed environment for one month. The concentration of U, Th, and K are illustrated in Table 1. In order to estimate the natural dose rate soil samples were collected from the site and U, Th, and K content analysis by gamma spectrometry Canberra GR4520 which has a low-level gamma spectrometry system with 15 cm lead shielding and high-resolution GeHP hyper pure germanium detector, having 43.5% resolution efficiency for 661.6 keV. ROSY software was used for calculating the sample's age. Dose rate and age calculation results are as follows: Environmental dose rate: 18.044 ± 0.2 Gy/ka and; Age of the sample: 5655 ± 233 years which are in line with the stratigraphically estimated age of this area.

Keywords: dating, radiochemical methodology, quartz, TL.

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